

Modelling Dynamic Controls on Cognitive Response of Users to Visual Stimulus

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Abstract

The concept used in systems on human physiology is very useful and plays an important role in the maintenance and internal stability based on environmental changes. The physiological systems are well known to be based on regulating the functions by mutual interaction between one part of the body and another and this is associated with the homeostasis of physiology than the related independent activities. Different methods have been known to be associated with the identification of different kinds of common interaction between the sensory organs connected to the brain and the peripheral devices we use for our everyday digital activities, this is basically to understand the connection and occurrence between the user brain and activity processes for ergonomics optimisation. This paper contributes to this field by integrating the dynamic control model with the physiological response modelling to determine the performance in the interaction with basic stimuli from user-generated data. The result shows that the skin temperature and skin conductance response play a prodigious role in the contribution of physiological parameters to predicting user activities and fixation duration has the least error in prediction from the dynamic control models. These parameters can be very useful in robotics for the design of physiological control systems that represent robot-user interactions.

Keywords: Physiological response model, Physiological Interaction, External Stimulus, Coupling, Modification

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1 Introduction

There are different methods that have been introduced to recognise different kinds of interactions between the physiological system based on biological signals like the

electroencephalogram (EEG), Electrocardiogram (ECG), and other respiratory activities. The experimental studies [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] on this have found that the common interaction between the physiological systems can

occur in both intra-inter individual singularity. Also, recent research [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13] on biological rhythms in physiological systems can be controlled by static coupling with external visual and auditory rhythmic stimuli [14, 15, 16]. The latest findings give experimental evidence of the interactions of physiological systems based on their biological signals on different conditions and statuses. But, a concise way of understanding this concept is necessary for the mechanics of the interaction and co-operation that leads to physiological functioning that is related to activities of the peripheral and nervous systems.

It is very important to understand these activities because they represent the direct association with the functioning of the physiological systems and the overall health and mental processes such as abnormal nervous activities that are related to the dis-functioning of the physiological systems. An advanced investigation is required on the knowledge related to the changes in our biological rhythms during interactions between activities of the nervous system and the physiological systems in different conditions. These investigations can apply non-invasive methods to improve the physical and mental workload of users. Furthermore, investigations can also extend the process to understand how the coordination of the physiological state e.g. patterns in eye movement behaviour between individuals is related to interactions of the physiological systems and the visual stimulus. The research topic can address current knowledge of the dynamics of the physiological system, particularly the one that is focused on the idea of the internal and external stimuli response.

Each stimulus response state can encompass changes in the physiological conditions that can be represented in a mathematical model derived from the natural human physiologic processes on a specified experimental setup. The external stimuli can then contain physical stimuli such as auditory and visual electrical stimuli, the method can be based on applications to improve the mental and physical workload of the user by modulating biological coupling with the dynamic control model and external stimuli like the procedure adopted in this paper. The dynamic control coupling with the physiological system (Equation 1) is a novel contribution to the field of design of physiological control systems and ergonomics optimisation.

$$R_{response} = \frac{d^n P_{response}}{dT_{secs}^n} + \frac{d^{n-1} P_{response}}{dT_{secs}^{n-1}} + \dots + \frac{dP_{response}}{dT_{secs}} + C \quad (1)$$

Where $R_{(response)}$ is the resultant response, $d^n P_{response}$ is the general physiological response within n time reactive interval with constant external reaction C which is coupled with the end product of the dynamic control model (Equation 2 and Figure 1).

$$\text{Dynamic model } \min_P \text{imise } \|y_t - y\|_n \quad (2)$$

$$\text{empirical process subject to } 0 = f\left(\frac{dx}{dt}, x, y, p\right) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{fundamental process } 0 \leq g\left(\frac{dx}{dy}, x, y, p\right) \quad (4)$$

$$(5)$$

2 Literature Review

The theory behind dynamic control relates to the control of dynamic systems [17, 18, 19, 20, 21] that are engineered with the process and mechanism of a machine. The main aim is to develop a model and an algorithm that governs the application of a system input that derives its systems mechanics to the desired state while minimising the delay and steady-state error that ensures a level of stability control aimed to a degree of optimality [22, 23]. A controller with requisite correction behaviour is needed to monitor the controlled process variable and compare it with a point set variable. The difference between an actual and predicted value of the control process is referred to as the error or error signal; this is set as the feedback to generate a control process variable [24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. When relating this to the physiological control system, the error can be in terms of mean square error (MSE) [28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] which is used to establish the reliability of the designed model obtained through coupling. Other aspects of error signal that are also studied are the observability and controllability of the dynamic model. This set a basis for the advanced type of automation used to revolutionise processes in manufacturing-like industries and communication fields of research.

The control feedback is usually done by taking a measurement using biological sensors in areas of physiological systems and using dimensional sensors in an industrial environment. This calculates adjustment that keeps the measured variable within a specified range using the final control element as the control value. The extensive dynamic control model is usually made as a form of diagrammatic style or block control diagram with transfer functions known as the system function or the network function. Most methods represent this in a mathematical model equation of the relation between the input and output processes as a form of differential equation that describes the system's concept. As much as control systems have major advantages in predicting physiological processes, they also have their drawbacks in the open-loop controller, to overcome this limitation the process introduces feedback to control the states and outputs of the dynamic changes of the system. A quantified output from a measuring sensor is used as the control signal, the feedback input which is a process in the closing loop and

Figure 1: Dynamic control system for physiological input reaction (x)

the disturbance rejection guarantees performance with model uncertainties in the case where the model structure does not fit the real processes and the model parameters are not based on exactness. The control dynamics is most suitable in predicting physiological processes in humans and can process a close to perfect result given that human behaviour and processes are very difficult to predict in terms of residuals outputs, for human behaviour processes, it reduces sensitivity to parameter variations thereby resulting to a close to hundred per-cent accuracy [36, 37, 38, 39, 40].

3 Method

The procedures used here are based on the physical coupling of the dynamic control model and the physiological response recordings from a predefined experimental setup where participants interacted with dynamic visual controls from webpages [41, 42] and their physiological response was recorded in synchronous (Figure 2) with the activities that resulted in two thousand instances. 70% of the data recorded was used for the training set and 30% for the test set. The physiological components involved are the skin conductance response (SCR), Skin temperature, Fixation duration, Pupil dilation, and Heart rate measure. The collected data is based on quantified signal response measured from either multimodal sensors or a single signal enquiring sensor. The resultant reaction generated from the user activity is represented by the following equation:

$$Y_{resultant} = \frac{d^3x}{dt^3} + \frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + \frac{dx}{dt} + D \quad (6)$$

And its predicted user response is based on the coupled equation:

$$R_{response_i} - R \frac{Y_{resultant}}{Resultant * D} + R_{response_i}(Y_{resultant}) = 0 \quad (7)$$

Where $Y_{resultant}$ represent the coupling action between the signal response or reaction to external stimulus which is proportional to the resultant response $R_{response_1}$. The process is also repeated in the second stage (Equation 11)

$$\begin{aligned} R_{response_2} - R \frac{Y_{resultant}}{Resultant * D} + R_{response_2}(Y_{resultant}) &= 0 \quad (8) \\ &\vdots \quad (9) \\ R_{response_m} - R \frac{Y_{resultant}}{Resultant * D} + R_{response_m}(Y_{resultant}) &= 0 \quad (10) \\ &\vdots \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

The reciprocally of the resultant response induces a neutral response in the second loop which is proportional to the ultimate resultant response $R_{response_m}$. The performance and reliability of the model are based on the MSE (Equation 12).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - \hat{Y}_i)^2 \quad (12)$$

- n = number of data points
- Y_i = observed values
- \hat{Y}_i = predicted values

With σ^2 represented as one in all signal propagation. The proceeding section discusses the resulting output obtained from the experiment and the error in model modulation and coupling function.

4 Result

The method adopted a technique for associating physiological process signal recordings with structures in a dynamic control process modelling. The coupling of the two concepts allows them to be used as complementary coding in conceptual modelling; the process coding is suitable for modelling how activities interact, while the physiological process modelling is suitable when one needs to make precise statements about certain activity that goes on in the body and eye movement behaviour. This ability to model certain aspects of both physiological and dynamic control within the process model is important in a distributed grouped experimental setup. The main purpose is to make apparent what affects the reorganisation of visual activity, predict user response and activities, and indicate how the process model may be used to drive certain development of physiological systems and their rules. The main aim of the paper is simply to determine the performance of the coupling process and its reliability for ergonomic purposes. Figure 3 shows the

Figure 2: Raw physiological response signal from experimental setup

performance from both training and test sets with SCR and skin temperature has the most contributing physiological response parameters that can help in predicting a user's response activities to the stimulus they interacted with a score of 0.98% and .92% on the first test set (Figure 3a). The pupil changes have a 100% performance on the fourth training set (Figure 3d). This is also similar to other research findings [] that there is a significant rule of pupillary measure to user perception and also its correlation to brain activity.

Error test was also computed for all the physiological parameters used based on MSE in Equation 12. To determine the congruency and consistency between variables, both training and test sets can equally be used to verify this concept; Figure 4a shows that skin temperature has the least error in the first test set and pupil dilation has the least error in the fourth training set. The reliability of a coupled model can be based on pupil dilation as an authentic physiological response parameter to determine or predict user activity when designing a physiological control system, both in robotics and other AI-designed tools.

5 Conclusion

This paper set out to test the performance metrics of dynamic controls on the physiological response of users to basic stimuli, this is a major research field that is part of the state of art research methods on physiological control systems. The paper contributes to this field by integrating the dynamic control model with the physiological response modelling to determine the performance in the interaction with basic stimuli from user-generated data. The result shows that the skin temperature and skin conductance response play a prodigious role in the contribution of physiological parameters to predicting user activ-

ities; pupil dilation fixation duration has the least error in prediction from the dynamic control models. These parameters can be very useful in robotics for the design of physiological control systems that represent robot-user interactions. Future perceptive would be to design a coding phase that would simulate the controls of user-robot interaction that would represent human emotional effects in robotics.

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(a) Error rate at first test

(b) Error rate at second training set

(c) Error rate at third training set

(d) Error rate at fourth training set

Figure 4: Different performance rate of training and test set of physiological response data

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